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Abstract	This report highlights the summary of progress and initial results in the context of the task 4.4.

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HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Reason of change
V0.1 (draft)	20 June 2025	The initial draft of the document is ready and ready for distribution between PERSEPHONE project partners to review.
V0.5	22 July 2025	Updated the report after an internal review
V1.0	30 July 2025	Final version ready

Executive summary

This deliverable, D4.4, reports the progress made in Task 4.4, which addresses real-time, infrastructure-free mapping and localization for autonomous robotic systems operating in underground mining environments. In such settings, machines cannot rely on pre-installed infrastructure like GPS, Wi-Fi, or Ultra-Wideband, and must instead depend entirely on onboard sensing to navigate and build maps collaboratively. The work presented here is part of a broader effort to enable safe and scalable autonomous operations in challenging, GPS-denied environments.

Building upon earlier project deliverables that explored navigation (D4.1), terrain analysis (D4.2), and traversability-aware planning (D4.3) which all relied on ground-truth simulation data this deliverable shifts the focus to evaluating SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) algorithms that operate solely on real sensor data, such as LiDAR and IMU. Two representative methods, LIO-SAM and DLIO, were selected and extensively tested in simulation using ROS 2 and Gazebo. Their performance was assessed in terms of localization accuracy and map quality within a simulated underground mine scenario.

In a multi-robot setup, two Terrain Hopper robots were deployed from different locations to generate partial maps of the mine. These maps were later successfully merged using descriptor-based scan matching techniques, demonstrating the feasibility of collaborative mapping without external infrastructure. Furthermore, this deliverable outlines a new communication architecture between explorer and deployer robots, leveraging mesh networking to enable real-time data sharing and coordination an aspect not covered in previous tasks. The results presented in this document represent an important milestone toward achieving autonomous, coordinated robotic exploration in infrastructure-deprived environments and lay the foundation for upcoming field evaluations in the next project phase.

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2 Introduction

The ability to perform real-time, autonomous mapping and localization in deep or abandoned mines is essential for ensuring safe and efficient robotic operations in environments that are inherently GPS-denied, communication-restricted, and structurally dynamic. In such underground scenarios, the absence of any pre-installed infrastructure like Wi-Fi or Ultra-Wideband (UWB) systems imposes significant challenges on conventional Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) pipelines. Consequently, a key objective of Task 4.4 is to explore and develop infrastructure-free mapping and localization approaches tailored specifically for such constrained environments.

This deliverable, D4.4, builds upon the groundwork laid in earlier phases by detailing the progress made toward multi-machine, infrastructure-independent SLAM and collaborative mapping. At the heart of our investigation is the use of LiDAR-based SLAM techniques that operate solely on onboard sensors namely LiDARs and IMUs without requiring any external localization infrastructure.

Two state-of-the-art SLAM frameworks, LIO-SAM and DLIO, were selected based on a preliminary survey of relevant literature and open-source implementations. These approaches were evaluated extensively in simulation using the ROS 2 Gazebo ecosystem. The simulated trials were performed on digital twin models of the Terrain Hopper robot, navigating through realistically modeled mine-like environments. Particular attention was given to understanding their performance in terms of localization accuracy, trajectory estimation consistency, and robustness to sensor noise and terrain variability. To extend this work to a multi-machine setting, we deployed two Terrain Hopper robots starting from distinct locations in the simulated mine. Each robot independently performed SLAM to generate point cloud maps (PCD) of the environment. These maps were then fused using a novel scan-matching and descriptor-based map merging strategy, enabling the creation of a unified, collaboratively built map. The merging process relied on identifying overlapping regions and establishing geometric correspondences across the individually built sub-maps, thereby demonstrating the feasibility of collaborative SLAM in an infrastructure-free setting.

In addition to the SLAM and mapping components, this deliverable also addresses the communication architecture necessary for real-time multi-machine coordination and data exchange. We explore various mesh networking approaches that are suitable for subterranean environments, where traditional networking solutions are either unavailable or unreliable. The document outlines how communication protocols and middleware like CycloneDDS are used for inter-robot and intra-system data sharing, enabling functionalities such as map distribution, loop closure detection, and shared task awareness. Together, the developments presented in this document provide a strong foundation for achieving scalable, infrastructure-free autonomy in complex underground environments, and serve as a critical steppingstone toward field deployment in the next phases of the project.

2.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the work conducted under Task 4.4 Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization, during the reporting period M9–M18 of the project. This task is led by LTU with contributions from UPAT, EPI, and MRP. The deliverable consolidates progress across several technical fronts, with the overarching goal of enabling a team of autonomous robotic systems to explore, map, and localize within underground mining environments without relying on any external infrastructure.

The specific objectives covered in this document include:

- Survey and evaluation of existing LiDAR + IMU-based SLAM algorithms suitable for underground operation using only onboard sensors.
- Simulation-based benchmarking of the selected SLAM algorithms (LIO-SAM and DLIO) in a ROS 2 Gazebo setup using a realistic Terrain Hopper robot model.
- Quantitative assessment of localization error and mapping quality in mine-like environments, including considerations for loop closure, odometry drift, and robustness to terrain complexity.
- Multi-machine collaborative mapping, where multiple robots autonomously generate partial maps which are later aligned and merged using descriptor-based scan matching approaches to build a global map.
- Design and analysis of mesh networking solutions that enable real-time coordination and data sharing among robots in the absence of Wi-Fi or similar infrastructure.
- Integration of communication middleware (e.g., CycloneDDS) to facilitate robot-to-robot and internal data communication for SLAM, navigation, and map updates.

The scope of this document is limited to simulation-based validation of the functionalities. While the communication architecture and multi-machine SLAM pipeline have been validated in software-in-the-loop simulations, full-scale hardware evaluations and field trials are planned for subsequent work packages.

This document provides not only a comprehensive technical evaluation of the systems developed so far but also acts as a foundation for future implementation and deployment in physical environments. It aims to highlight lessons learned, identify remaining challenges, and inform the integration strategies for real-world mining use cases.

2.2 Related documents

This deliverable builds directly on the outcomes of D4.1, D4.2, and D4.3, which focused on various foundational aspects of autonomous navigation in

underground mining environments. Specifically, D4.1 explored basic motion planning and navigation strategies, D4.2 addressed terrain analysis and traversability assessment using onboard perception, and D4.3 advanced the planning pipeline by incorporating multi-criteria decision-making for navigation over complex terrain. However, an important distinction between these earlier deliverables and the present work is the source of localization data used for mapping. In D4.1 through D4.3, mapping and navigation relied on ground truth odometry provided by the Gazebo simulation environment. While this offered reliable localization for the purpose of evaluating planners and terrain reasoning algorithms, it does not reflect the challenges of real-world deployment where such ground truth is unavailable.

In contrast, this progress report focuses on the development and evaluation of SLAM algorithms that operate directly on raw sensor inputs, specifically LiDAR and IMU data. These algorithms provide real-time localization and mapping capabilities without relying on any infrastructure or externally provided pose estimates. This shift is critical for enabling full autonomy in real-world subterranean settings where no prior maps or external references are available. Furthermore, this document introduces the communication architecture between explorer and deployer machines, a key system component that was not addressed in earlier tasks. The architecture supports infrastructure-free coordination and data sharing, enabling collaborative map building and situational awareness across multiple autonomous agents. This addition significantly enhances the system's overall autonomy and scalability.

3 Technical Details

3.1 Survey existing LiDAR and IMU-based SLAM approaches

A survey on available LiDAR inertial odometry (LIO) packages was conducted. Primarily focusing on LIO-SAM and DLIO due to their promising characteristics that will be expanded upon. In addition to the above-mentioned packages, other LIO and SLAM packages with less favorable characteristics are presented and compared with LIO-SAM and DLIO.

Firstly, DLIO and its characteristics will be examined. Direct LiDAR-Inertial Odometry DLIO was developed to operate in environments where the terrain is irregular, such environments due to aggressive motions generated by traversing it induce motion distortion in LiDAR scans degrading localization and mapping (Chen et al., 2023). In addition, DLIO is a lightweight package regarding computational demands, according to the metrics provided in Chen et al.'s paper DLIO is 20% more computationally efficient than the current state-of-the-art coupled with a 12% increase in accuracy (Chen et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, DLIO has a major con; it lacks loop closure. Comparing LiDAR and IMU-based SLAM approaches for 3D robotic mapping, algorithms that did not perform loop closure were found lacking when conducting long surveys to such an extent that some features appear doubled (Tiozzo et al., 2023).

LIO-SAM estimates trajectory and conducts map-building for a mobile robot in real-time. LIO-SAM functions by constructing a lidar-inertial odometry on top of a factor graph, for the initial LiDAR odometry optimization guess and de-skewing of the point cloud is achieved by the estimate motion the IMU generates (Tixiao et al., 2020). LIO-SAM, unlike DLIO, includes loop closure, by that fact alone it is more suitable for long running operations. LIO-SAM's scan-matching is achieved at a local scale instead of global to increase performance (Tixiao et al., 2020). It should be mentioned that pointcloud deskewing is the correction of errors on the pointcloud due to motion distortion from the movement of the mobile vehicle that performs SLAM. (Zhao et al, 2024).

In the related literature two tests were conducted for the comparison of the LIO-SAM and the DLIO algorithms. Results from the tests are depicted in the tables below. Table 1 shows the results in the Newer College dataset where the root mean square error (RMSE) value of the absolute trajectory error is calculated, as well as the average computation time. Table 2 shows the results from the test conducted on the UCLA campus dataset with metrics the average computational time and the end-to-end translational error.

Table 1 Test conducted on Newer College dataset (Chen et al., 2023). Comparison between LIO-SAM and different iterations of DLIO, focusing on absolute trajectory error (trajectory error between the sensor generated path compared to the ground truth path). *No motion correction. **Correction in discrete-time trajectory using only integration of the IMU measurements between two LiDAR sweeps. ***Full continuous-time motion correction.

Algorithm	Absolute Trajectory Error (RMSE) [m]					Avg Comp. [ms]
	Short (1609.40m)	Long (3063.42m)	Quad (479.04m)	Dynamic (97.20m)	Park (695.68m)	
DLIO (None)*	0.4299	0.3988	0.1117	0.1959	0.1821	34.88
DLIO (Discrete)**	0.3803	0.3629	0.0943	0.0798	0.1537	34.61
DLIO (Continuous)***	0.3606	0.3268	0.0837	0.0612	0.1196	35.74
LIO-SAM	0.3957	0.4092	0.0950	0.0973	0.1761	179.33

Table 2 Test conducted on the UCLA campus dataset (Chen et al., 2023) calculating the end-to-end translational error and average computational time.

Algorithm	End-to-End Translational Error [m]				Avg. Comp. [ms]			
	A (652.66m)	B (526.58m)	C (551.38m)	D (530.75m)	A	B	C	D
DLIO	0.0105	0.0233	0.0301	0.0082	10.45	8.37	8.66	10.96
LIO-SAM	0.0216	0.0692	0.0936	0.0249	33.21	29.14	39.04	48.94

Table 3 Characteristics of the compared algorithms.

	RTAB-Map	LeGO-LOAM	LIO-SAM	hdl_graph	DLO	FAST-LIO2	DLIO
Scan matching	ICP	ICP	ICP	NDT	G-ICP	x	G-ICP
Downsampling						x	
Feature extraction	x	Edges, planes, ground	Edges, planes	x	Ground	x	x
Loop closure					x	x	x
LiDAR-IMU fusion	Loose	Loose	Tight	Loose	Loose	Tight	Loose

On Table 3, characteristics or lack thereof of the different SLAM algorithms are depicted. Regarding scan matching the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm is used for aligning two surfaces (usually represented by mesh grids). In the case of PERSEPHONE, this algorithm is used to align consecutive two pointcloud frames created by the 3D LiDAR based the distance between the points of the two frames. Additionally, Normal Distribution Transformation (NDT) is another frequently used scan matching algorithm that utilises a Gaussian distribution to model point clouds. Finally, Generalised-ICP (G-ISP) is a variation and an improvement of the ICP algorithm that utilises as distance metrics the point-to-point distance and the point to plane distance in a probabilistic framework to align the pointcloud frames.

Table 4 4 Applications of IMU in the compared algorithms.

Algorithm	Deskewing		Motion prediction		LiDAR-IMU calibration
	Angular velocity	Linear acceleration	Angular velocity	Linear acceleration	
RTAB-Map	X	X			User defined
LeGO-LOAM			x	x	X
LIO-SAM					User defined
hdl_graph					User defined
DLO		x		x	X
FAST-LIO2	X	x		x	Estimated online
DLIO					User defined

As depicted in Table 4, hdl-graph seems to be a valid candidate to be used for mapping and localization. However, when it is used in GPS-denied areas the algorithm always considers the ground as a level plane which is highly inaccurate in the case of deep and abandoned mines. Additionally, without access to GPS, the algorithm cannot perform loop closures (Koide et al., 2019).

3.2 Evaluate selected SLAM solutions in gazebo simulation.

As mentioned earlier, LIO-SAM and DLIO are two potential candidates from the current state of the art of the LiDAR and IMU based SLAM algorithms that could be utilized in an underground mining environment where there is no access to Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS). Furthermore, especially in the case of abandoned mines where the environment usually lacks adequate illumination, using other types of algorithms such visual based SLAM algorithms can be rather challenging. Therefore, the use of LiDAR and inertial based algorithms could provide more adequate results in such cases.

In this Section, the SLAM packages will be integrated into the Terrain Hopper vehicle used in the Gazebo simulation and will be evaluated based on their odometry and localization errors that are accumulated as the operation time increases. The evaluation was conducted with the use of the evo library in Python which compares and evaluates the trajectory output of odometry and SLAM algorithms.

To evaluate them the following scenario takes place. A single Terrain Hopper vehicle maps part of the abandoned mine of the simulation creating a pointcloud. Its position and orientation with respect to the world frame of the Gazebo is recorded and it is used as the ground truth for the pose of the robot. At the same time each algorithm publishes a topic which contains the pose information of the robot with respect to the map coordinate frame based on the lidar and odometry data. The two topics mentioned above are the only data that are needed to evaluate the odometry and localization errors. When testing each package, the

Terrain Hopper begins from the same initial position, and it follows a very similar trajectory in both cases.

Before evaluating the SLAM packages, the following preprocessing steps are performed on the data. Firstly, the ground truth trajectory and the trajectory estimated from the SLAM package are synchronized by matching their timestamps with a tolerance of 10ms. Messages that are not synchronized are discarded. Secondly, the poses estimated from the SLAM package are transformed so that they can be expressed with respect to the world coordinate frame of the simulation so that they can be comparable with the ground truth poses. After those two steps the evo library can be used to evaluate the results of the algorithms.

The metrics that are calculated through the library are the Absolute Trajectory Error (ATE) and the Relative Trajectory Error (RTE).

- **ATE:** ATE is the difference between the estimated pose of the robot and the actual (ground truth) pose of the robot at any given time.
- **RTE:** RTE is the difference in the robot's movement over a set distance or interval. This metric compares the estimated change in the pose of the robot (estimated relative pose) to the actual change in the pose of the robot (ground truth relative pose). In this evaluation RTE is calculated between two consecutive poses of the robot.

Below the resulting maps from LIO-SAM (Figure 1) and DLIO (Figure 2) are depicted.

Figure 1 Resulted point cloud of the abandoned mine using LIO-SAM.

Figure 2 Resulted point cloud of the abandoned mine using DLIO.

In hindsight the two pointclouds generated from the two packages seem very similar. However, it should be noted that the resulting pointcloud from LIO-SAM is significantly denser than the one generated with the aid of DLIO. More specifically, The DLIO pointcloud consists of 88506 points while the LIO-SAM pointcloud consists of 264200 points, which is 298.5% the number of points of the DLIO map. For further evaluation the ATE and RTE from the integration of the LIO-SAM algorithm will be examined. Then, the same evaluation will be conducted for the integration of the DLIO algorithm. Finally, the results of the two algorithms will be compared.

3.2.1 Evaluation of the LIO-SAM algorithm in the simulated environment.

Figure 3 3D plot of the ground truth (dashed lines) and the estimated trajectory (multi-color line) produced using the LIO-SAM algorithm with respect to the simulation's world frame. The colormap shows the ATE regarding the translational part of the trajectory in meters.

Figure 3 depicts the three-dimensional representation in space of the ground truth trajectory (dashed line) and the LIO-SAM estimated trajectory (multi-colored line). Both trajectories are plotted with respect to the simulation's world coordinate frame. The colormap depicts the ATE error regarding the translational part of the trajectory in meters. As it might be noticeable the increase in the translational error is mostly due to a significant deviation in the z coordinate and it can reach up to 10.55m.

Figure 4 Trajectory estimated with the LIO-SAM algorithm analyzed in the XYZ coordinates compared with the ground truth. Ground truth trajectory in each coordinate is depicted with a black line while the estimated trajectories in the x, y and z axes are depicted

In Figure 4, the estimated and the ground truth trajectories are analyzed in XYZ coordinates. The maximum error in each coordinate is 0.81m along the X-axis, 2.72m along the Y-axis and 10.22m along the Z-axis.

Figure 5 Orientation estimated with the LIO-SAM algorithm analyzed in WXYZ coordinates of the Unit quaternion. The W coordinate is the scalar part of the quaternion.

In Figure 5, the estimated orientation with the use of LIO-SAM algorithm is analyzed to the quaternion coordinates and compared with the orientation of the ground truth. The maximum ATE regarding the rotational part of the trajectory was approximately 12.44°.

Figure 6 ATE of the translation part of the LIO-SAM's estimated trajectory.

Figure 7 ATE of the rotational part of the LIO-SAM's estimated trajectory.

In Figure 6 and Figure 7, the ATE of the translational part and rotational part are depicted, respectively. Regarding the translational part it begins with a very small value of approximately 0.03m and reaches a value of 10.55m. As it is already mentioned, the increase in error is mostly due to a large deviation in the estimation of the altitude of the robot (trajectory on the Z-axis). At around 270s after the mapping operation has begun the robot turns around to attempt to perform loop closure. Therefore, the Terrain Hopper begins backtracking the part of the tunnel that in the beginning it was descending. Regarding the rotational part the minimum ATE is approximately 1.5° and reaches momentarily a maximum at 12.44° while the mean and root mean square error (RMSE) are ~3.77° and ~4.18°, respectively. It can be noticed that the orientation of the robot is not estimated correctly from the beginning of the mapping procedure which is something that must be investigated further in WP5.

Figure 8 RTE of the translation part of the LIO-SAM's estimated trajectory.

Figure 9 RTE of the rotational part of the LIO-SAM's estimated trajectory.

In Figure 8 and Figure 9, the RTE of the translational and rotational parts are depicted to evaluate the performance of the LIO-SAM algorithm. Regarding the translational part the minimum RTE is $\sim 0\text{m}$ while the maximum is $\sim 0.4\text{m}$. The mean translational RTE is $\sim 0.02\text{m}$ while RMSE is $\sim 0.03\text{m}$. From these metrics it is reasonable to see how when the RTE accumulates it can lead to a constant increase in the translational ATE. Regarding the rotational RTE, it has a minimum value of $\sim 0^\circ$ and a momentary maximum value of $\sim 9.2^\circ$. Important to metrics are, also, the mean value ($\sim 0.24^\circ$), the RMSE ($\sim 0.45^\circ$) and the standard deviation (0.38°).

3.2.2 Evaluation of the DLIO algorithm in the simulated environment.

Figure 10 3D plot of the ground truth and the estimated trajectory produced using the DLIO algorithm with respect to the simulation's world frame. The colormap shows the ATE regarding the translational part of the trajectory in meters. The multicolor line represents the estimated trajectory, while the dashed line represents the ground truth trajectory.

Figure 10 depicts the estimated trajectory created using DLIO (multi-colored line) and it is compared with the ground truth trajectory (dashed line). The colormap shows the color based on the translational ATE. In this occasion, it can be noticed a higher error in the Z-axis as well as a significant deviation in the X-axis while towards the negative X-axis.

Figure 11 Trajectory estimated with the DLIO algorithm analyzed in the XYZ coordinates compared with the ground truth. Ground truth trajectory in each coordinate is depicted with a black line while the estimated trajectories in the X, Y and Z are depicted with a red, a green and a blue line, respectively.

In Figure 11, the estimated trajectory generated with DLIO is analyzed in the XYZ-coordinates and the maximum error in each coordinate is $\sim 2.68\text{m}$ in the X-axis, $\sim 1.39\text{m}$ in the Y-axis and $\sim 16.79\text{m}$ on the Z-axis. In all three axis the error

is larger compared to the error in the LIO-SAM case.

Figure 12 Orientation estimated with the DLIO algorithm analyzed in WXYZ coordinates of the Unit quaternion. *w* coordinate is the scalar part.

Figure 12 depicts the estimated orientation in quaternion form analysed in the four elements of the quaternion compared to the ground truth orientation. The maximum ATE regarding the rotational part of the trajectory was approximately $\sim 20.08^\circ$.

Figure 13 ATE of the translation part of the DLIO's estimated trajectory.

Figure 14 ATE of the rotational part of the DLIO's estimated trajectory.

In Figure 13 and Figure 14, the ATE of the translational part and rotational part are depicted. Regarding the translational part it begins with a very small value of approximately 0m and reaches a value of 17.01m. Due to accumulated localisation errors as the operational time increases so does ATE. The trajectory of the robot is almost the same as the one in the case of LIO-SAM. This is the reason why ATE is reduced after 310 seconds of operation, since the robot turns back and begins to ascend the tunnel. Regarding the rotational part the minimum ATE is approximately 0° and reaches a maximum at ~20.01° while the mean and root mean square error (RMSE) are ~9° and ~10.37°, respectively. A few seconds after the SLAM task begins a sudden increase in the rotational ATE can be noticed. This occurs because that is when the robot begins to move. DLIO does not begin to calculate the robot's pose if the robot doesn't begin to move.

Figure 15 RTE of the translation part of the DLIO's estimated trajectory.

Figure 16 RTE of the translation part of the DLIO's estimated trajectory.

In Figure 15 and Figure 16, the RTE of the translational and rotational parts are depicted in order to evaluate the performance of the DLIO algorithm. Regarding the translational part the minimum RTE is $\sim 0\text{m}$ while the maximum is $\sim 0.12\text{m}$. The mean translational RTE is $\sim 0.003\text{m}$ while RMSE is $\sim 0.01\text{m}$. Regarding the rotational RTE that it has a minimum value of $\sim 0^\circ$ and a momentary maximum value of $\sim 3.82^\circ$. Important to metrics are, also, the mean value ($\sim 0.039^\circ$), the RMSE ($\sim 0.086^\circ$) and the standard deviation (0.079°).

3.2.3 Comparing results of LIO-SAM and DLIO

The results of both the DLIO and the LIO-SAM algorithm are presented in Table 5 and Table 6. When comparing the two, it is evident that although both algorithms were tested on similar trajectories of comparable length, DLIO estimated the Terrain Hopper's trajectory to be 34 meters longer than the actual path (an overestimation of 21.2%), whereas LIO-SAM overestimated the length by only 3.8 meters (2.6%). Additionally, DLIO seemed to have a larger maximum ATE in comparison with DLIO both regarding the translational and the rotational part. The better performance of the LIO-SAM algorithm regarding the ATE error can be partly attributed to the fact that LIO-SAM utilises loop closure to reduce accumulated odometry error. However, DLIO had a smaller RTE error regarding all the metrics that were used for the evaluation of the two packages.

Table 5 ATE of DLIO and LIO-SAM as well as the trajectory length in each case in the simulated environment.

Algorithm	Trajectory length		Absolute Trajectory Error (ATE)			
	Ground truth(m)	Estimated (m)	Max. tran. error (m)	Min tran. error (m)	Max rot. error (degrees)	Min rot. error (degrees)
DLIO	160.66	194.66	17.01	0	20.08	0
LIO-SAM	146.90	150.70	10.55	0.03	12.44	1.50

Table 6 RTE of DLIO and LIO-SAM from the simulated environment.

Absolute Trajectory Error (RTE)										
Algorithm	Translational RTE (meters)					Rotational RTE (degrees)				
	Max	Min	Mean	Standard deviation	RMSE	Max	Min	Mean	Standard deviation	RMSE
DLIO	0.12	0.003	0.006	0.008	0.01	3.82	0	0.039	0.08	0.09
LIO-SAM	0.40	0	0.02	0.02	0.03	9.20	0	0.24	0.38	0.45

3.3 Generate 3D maps of the simulated abandoned and deep mining environments in gazebo simulation.

The SLAM packages evaluated on Section 3.4 were used to create 3D maps of the abandoned mine areas in the simulated environment. More specifically, two terrain hoppers were used in two different scenarios to map different parts of the mine. Each one of them was running the same SLAM package. In the first scenario, the two terrain hoppers begin mapping in different locations of the mine and meet at the starting area of the second scenario. In the second scenario, both terrain hoppers commence the mapping procedure beginning from the same area where there are only two tunnels leading to different parts of the mine.

Figure 17 Starting area of the two terrain hoppers in the abandoned mine case in the second scenario, as well as the meeting for the two terrain hoppers in the first scenario.

The resulting maps from each scenario were utilized in Section 3.6.

3.4 Merge the generated maps using novel map merging approaches.

In multi-robot exploration and inspection missions, especially in complex and large-scale environments such as underground mines, the ability to merge individual robot-generated maps into a consistent global representation is crucial. Map merging enables collaborative autonomy, shared situational awareness, and mission-level coordination. Without it, each robot operates within its own local reference frame, severely limiting multi-agent cooperation and integration.

Task 3.6 addresses this need by investigating novel map merging strategies tailored for subterranean robotic operations. Given the variability in environmental and communication conditions underground, we consider two primary paradigms:

- **Centralized Map Merging:** In centralized systems, robots maintain frequent or continuous communication, either directly or via infrastructure (e.g., Wi-Fi relays near the surface). This enables the incremental sharing of individual LiDAR scans or partial maps during the mission. Such systems support progressive map fusion and are effective in well-connected areas, typically closer to the surface or in established tunnel segments where communication networks can be deployed.
- **Decentralized Map Merging upon Rendezvous:** In contrast, decentralized strategies are necessary in environments where persistent communication is not feasible. In these cases, robots may operate independently for extended periods and exchange data only upon physical rendezvous. Rather than transmitting every scan, agents share their full accumulated local maps during these short contact events. This scenario is more common in newly explored or deeper sections of the mine, where infrastructure is sparse or non-existent.

Both approaches are examined within Deliverable D4.4, recognizing that a hybrid operational strategy may be required. Mining environments often include both well-instrumented areas and newly developed, infrastructure-less zones. As such, the ability to switch between centralized and decentralized map merging paradigms, or to operate in a mixed mode, is essential for robust deployment.

The methods developed under this task focus on solving the challenges of inter-map alignment, transformation estimation, and robust loop closure, even when input data is sparse, partially overlapping, or noisy. The outcome supports the creation of unified multi-robot maps, which are foundational for cooperative planning, shared risk assessment, and autonomous operation in GPS-denied environments.

3.6.2 Methods Overview

To support the integration of individual robot maps into a coherent global representation, we explore two complementary approaches to map merging: one tailored for centralized communication scenarios, and another for decentralized

rendezvous-based operations. Both are evaluated within the context of underground robotic missions where communication conditions vary spatially and temporally.

Centralized Map Merging – FRAME-Based Pipeline:

For centralized operations, where robots can maintain frequent or continuous communication, we employ the FRAME map merging framework developed by LTU. This approach enables progressive, scan-level fusion of maps during the mission and is optimized for robustness and computational efficiency.

Each robot independently collects LiDAR scans and extracts place recognition descriptors during navigation. These descriptors are compact vectors that encode place-dependent and yaw-invariant information, suitable for matching similar regions regardless of orientation. Robots periodically exchange descriptor arrays, allowing for inter-robot comparison to identify overlapping areas in their respective maps.

Once an overlapping region is detected:

1. The trajectory points corresponding to the matched descriptors are used to extract submaps from each robot’s local map.
2. An initial transformation is estimated using the descriptor match and relative positions.
3. The submaps are then aligned using Generalized Iterative Closest Point (GICP) to obtain a refined transformation with high geometric precision.

This refined transformation is then integrated into a global pose graph, which allows for full-system global optimization, reducing drift and refining the pose estimates of all participating agents. This process can be repeated throughout the mission to incrementally fuse maps and correct accumulated odometry error.

Figure 18 : Overall map merging pipeline of FRAME. While the robots r_1 and r_2 explore the surroundings, they collect the vector sets Q and W . A predefined event will trigger the merging process, and as an egocentric approach, each robot will create its own merged map M , maintaining its local map frame as the global frame.

Decentralized Map Merging – Rendezvous-Based Global Registration

In scenarios where robots cannot communicate continuously, such as in deeper or newly explored parts of a mine, a decentralized approach is required. In this setup, robots operate independently and exchange full local point cloud maps only upon

physical rendezvous. The map merging process is then performed offline or on the spot using global registration techniques.

Although the FRAME pipeline can theoretically be adapted to this case, by exchanging descriptors and matching them post-hoc, the decentralized strategy explored in this deliverable focuses on direct point cloud registration using state-of-the-art methods. Specifically, we evaluate:

- **KISS-Matcher:** A fast and robust global point cloud registration system optimized for both scan-level and map-level alignment. KISS-Matcher builds on classical geometric pipelines but introduces significant performance and scalability enhancements:
 - Uses a custom feature descriptor called Faster-PFH, an optimized version of Fast Point Feature Histograms [1].
 - Applies k-core-based graph-theoretic outlier pruning to filter correspondences efficiently.
 - Employs a Graduated Non-Convexity (GNC) solver for robust pose estimation without requiring initial alignment.
 - Demonstrates excellent scalability and speed, outperforming TEASER++ and other robust registration methods in large-scale, multi-robot scenarios.
- **Super4PCS:** A linear-time global registration algorithm that aligns raw point clouds in arbitrary poses using a minimal set of congruent 4-point bases:
 - Efficiently identifies geometric congruencies between point sets using smart indexing and output-sensitive pairing strategies.
 - Requires no initial pose estimate and works well with low-overlap and noisy datasets, ideal for sparse underground maps.
 - Offers significant speed-ups over traditional 4PCS by reducing the number of redundant congruent candidates and efficiently pruning the search space

Both methods are fully compatible with decentralized rendezvous scenarios and require only the local point cloud maps to be shared at the time of contact. They serve as drop-in components for aligning and merging robot maps in communication-constrained environments.

3.6.3 Evaluation Setup

To validate the robustness and flexibility of the proposed map merging approaches, we designed a series of controlled evaluations covering both centralized and decentralized paradigms. The experiments were conducted using a combination of benchmark datasets, simulated mining scenarios, and real-world deployments, reflecting the communication and environmental diversity expected in underground exploration.

Centralized Map Merging Evaluation – FRAME

The FRAME map merging framework was tested under both benchmark and real-world conditions to assess its alignment precision, descriptor robustness, and runtime performance.

- **Descriptor Modularity:** The descriptor matching component of FRAME is designed to be modular, supporting any descriptor that provides translation and rotation invariance. This allows the framework to adapt to different sensor configurations or mission requirements without structural modification.
- **KITTI Case Study:** A preliminary evaluation was conducted using the KITTI odometry dataset, where the recall rate of overlapping locations, yaw invariance of the descriptors, and inference and query times were benchmarked. The results demonstrate that the chosen descriptors reliably identify loop closures under varying viewpoints and sensor poses, supporting efficient submap alignment.
- **Real-World Tunnel Deployments:** Two underground test environments were used to validate the FRAME pipeline in operational conditions:
 - LTU Underground Robotics Lab (Figure 19).

Figure 19 : Example maps from LTU's subterranean laboratory where robots explore different parts used for the evaluation of the map merging algorithm.

- Partnered Swedish Mine: A field deployment involving autonomous robot runs in an unstructured, real-world mine setting. The merging of maps created by different agents demonstrated the framework's

capacity to align large-scale point clouds despite drift and limited overlap (Figure 20).

Figure 20 : 3D point cloud maps from a partner mine in Sweden, depicting different tunnel sections explored by robots.

Decentralized Map Merging Evaluation – KISS-Matcher and Super4PCS

For the decentralized setting, we evaluated KISS-Matcher and Super4PCS on simulated underground maps provided by UPAT. The focus here is on scenarios where robots operate independently and exchange maps only upon rendezvous.

Two simulation scenarios were constructed:

- **Scenario A:** Robots begin at different tunnel locations and meet midway during their exploration (Figure 21). Each robot builds an independent point cloud map prior to data exchange.

Figure 21: Scenario A point cloud maps provided by UPAT using LIO-SAM in a simulation environment. The maps are initially misaligned due to differing robot starting positions.

- **Scenario B – Shared Start with Diverging Paths:** Robots start from a common origin point and explore different directions, simulating a coordinated but disconnected exploration mission (Figure 22).

Figure 22 : Scenario B point cloud maps provided by UPAT using LIO-SAM in a simulation environment. The maps are initially misaligned due to differing robot starting positions.

3.6.4 Results

Starting with FRAME and the descriptor evaluation on KITTI. The Figure X shows the recall performance for the top-k candidates for the following descriptor extraction.

A. Place Recognition Analysis (KITTI Evaluation)

To assess the descriptor matching component of FRAME, we conducted a comparative evaluation on the KITTI dataset. *Figure X* shows the top-k recall rates for several state-of-the-art place recognition methods, including both learning-based and handcrafted descriptors.

Among the top performers, Overlap Transformer showed excellent recall and yaw invariance, benefiting from its transformer-based architecture. However, its reliance on large datasets and lack of yaw discrepancy modules limit its applicability in underground settings. Overlap Net also performed well using only range images but suffers from decreased robustness under rotational shifts.

More practical options include OREOS and 3DEG, which offer lightweight architectures, consistent yaw invariance, and fast processing. Notably, 3DEG extends OREOS by incorporating topological cues to improve recognition in feature-sparse environments. LiDAR-Iris and Scan Context, while non-learning-based, provided competitive recall. However, Scan Context lacks yaw invariance, and LiDAR-Iris is less efficient in all-to-all matching.

B. Runtime Analysis

Runtime evaluations were conducted on a mobile-grade CPU (Intel i7-1165G7), measuring the performance of each module within the FRAME pipeline. Processing time was broken down into: descriptor extraction (with preprocessing), querying, submap sampling, GICP alignment, and total time.

- **Descriptor Extraction:** Learning-based methods like OREOS and 3DEG were the most efficient (fast CNN+MLP), while LiDAR-Iris and Scan Context had higher costs due to hand-crafted pipeline stages. OverlapNet required additional normal estimation, increasing preprocessing time.
- **Querying Time:** Since map merging performs all-to-all matching between descriptor stacks, efficiency is crucial. OREOS and 3DEG used compact 64-D descriptors with fast k-d tree search, resulting in the best performance. LiDAR-Iris and OverlapNet showed poor scalability due to binary descriptors and large multidimensional data, respectively. Overlap Transformer offered both slow direct querying and a faster k-d tree variant using its 256-D descriptors.

Overall, all frameworks achieved processing rates suitable for real-time deployment (5–30 Hz), meeting the operational constraints for mobile robots navigating at 1–3 m/s. The combination of descriptor compactness, yaw robustness, and fast querying makes OREOS and 3DEG particularly well suited for integration within the FRAME-based map merging system.

C. FRAME - Merged Results

1) Underground Tunnel System

FRAME was first evaluated on two maps collected in our subterranean tunnel environment, as visualized in *Figure X*. The maps, M1 and M2, consist of approximately 150,000 points each, covering 136 m and 257 m respectively. M1 was generated using LIO-SAM on a quadrotor platform, while M2 was produced by a legged robot using DLO, resulting in different point densities and sensor configurations, characteristics of a multimodal setup.

Despite an initial yaw difference of $\sim 180^\circ$, the pipeline successfully detected 33% map overlap, correctly identifying a junction region and regressing the rotational offset in approximately 0.25 seconds. The resulting transformation achieved a translation error of $T_e = 0.09$ m and a rotation error of $R_e = 3.43^\circ$, demonstrating FRAME's robustness in cross-platform and orientation-discrepant scenarios.

2) Multibranch Junction in Subterranean Mine

A second evaluation was conducted in a real mining site, featuring a multi-branch junction. The two maps, M1 and M2, were generated by a robot traversing diverging paths through the junction, each capturing 2.8 million points across 145 m using an Ouster OS1-32 LiDAR sensor.

With an initial relative rotation of $\sim 45^\circ$ and 31% overlap, the system was challenged with structural complexity and partial visibility. Nonetheless, FRAME successfully aligned the maps using spherical subregions centered near the junction (radius $r = 10$ m), identifying sufficient shared geometry for reliable registration. The system achieved a translation error of $T_e = 0.082$ m, completing the alignment in just over 0.2 seconds.

This experiment confirms FRAME’s capability to operate effectively in large-scale, structurally complex, and partially overlapping subterranean environments, with minimal error and fast convergence.

D. KISS-Matcher and Super4PCS - Results

To evaluate the applicability of global registration methods in rendezvous-based decentralized map merging, we tested KISS-Matcher and Super4PCS on two simulated scenarios, as outlined in Section 3.6.3. The performance of each method is summarized in *Table X*, where we report translation error (e_{trans}), rotation error (e_{rot}), and total processing time. Since both methods estimate an initial alignment mainly, we also evaluate a refinement step using Generalized Iterative Closest Point (GICP) initialized with their output.

Scenario A – Disjoint Start with Rendezvous

In this scenario, robots begin exploration from different ends of the tunnel and meet mid-mission. Here:

- **KISS-Matcher** was unable to compute a valid transformation, likely due to insufficient correspondences under low overlap.
- **Super4PCS**, in contrast, successfully produced an alignment, which, after refinement with GICP, resulted in a translation error of 0.1663 m and rotation error of 1.82°, with a total runtime of 1.63 seconds.

Figure 23: Result of the map merging process in scenario A, using the Super4PCS + GICP pipeline, showing successful alignment of the previously misaligned maps.

Scenario B – Shared Start with Diverging Paths

In the second scenario, robots start together and explore different branches. Here, the results are reversed:

- **KISS-Matcher** performed reliably, delivering a high-quality initial alignment. With GICP refinement, the final translation error dropped to just 0.0035 m and rotation error to 0.036°, in a total processing time of 0.135 seconds.

- **Super4PCS** failed to register the maps in this case, likely due to the symmetry and lack of distinctive planar features in the diverging branches.

Figure 24: Result of the map merging process in scenario B, using the KISS-Matcher + GICP pipeline, showing successful alignment of the previously misaligned maps.

	Metrics	KISS-Matcher	KISS-Matcher + GICP	Super4PCS	Super4PCS +GICP
Scenario A	e_{trans} [m]	Failed		5.6357	0.1663
	e_{rot} [deg]			6.2989	1.8246
	time [sec]			1.55	1.63
Scenario B	e_{trans} [m]	0.0513	0.0035	Failed	
	e_{rot} [deg]	1.4374	0.0359		
	time [sec]	0.075	0.135		

Implementation Note

It is important to mention that the evaluated maps in both decentralized scenarios were generated using LIO-SAM, which provides sufficiently dense and consistent point clouds suitable for registration. Additional experiments were conducted using maps from DLIO, but these maps were found to be too sparse for reliable correspondence estimation, leading to failures in both KISS-Matcher and Super4PCS pipelines. However, this limitation is not expected to persist in future applications, as a custom mapping module with controllable map density output has already been developed. This module can be integrated into any odometry pipeline, ensuring that future deployments can dynamically adjust point cloud density to meet the requirements of the map merging framework, regardless of the underlying SLAM system.

3.5 Survey of available mesh networking solutions for infrastructure free map sharing among different machines.

It is essential to ensure reliable communication for coordination and data sharing among robotic agents in underground environments within the context of the PERSEPHONE project. Due to the absence of external infrastructure such as GPS, Wi-Fi, or cellular networks, the project aims to develop a robust and flexible communication system to support autonomous multi-robot operations and seamless map exchange. This section outlines the challenges of underground communication, including the lack of pre-existing wireless networks, and it highlights the need of custom networking architectures and communication protocols to ensure connectivity, coordination, and map sharing during autonomous missions. An overview of available mesh solutions for robotics use of multi robot deployment is necessary to assess future deployments. Notable, the DARPA SubT Challenge (2018-2021) highlighted these issues and demonstrated effective solutions developed by competing teams.

3.5.1 Team CERBERUS (Winner of the SubT Final Event).

Challenges:

- Large underground spaces lack any existing network infrastructure.
- Maintaining communication between multiple robots in extended tunnel networks was difficult.

Solutions:

- Utilized multi-hop mesh networking where robots relay signals to each other dynamically.
- Deployed Wi-Fi repeater nodes along the robots' paths to extend communication coverage.

3.5.2 Team CSIRO Data61 (Second Place Overall).

Challenges:

- Signal loss in tunnel bends, and vertical shafts disrupted robot coordination.
- Deep environments require extended communication range.

Solutions:

- Developed autonomous communication node deployment, where small relay devices were dropped along the robots' path to maintain a connection with the base station.
- Used a hybrid communication system combining Wi-Fi, LoRa, and UWB (Ultra-Wideband) to optimize coverage.

3.5.3 Team Explorer (CMU & OSU Collaboration, Winner of Tunnel Circuit).

Challenges:

- Large industrial and cave environments had no centralized network infrastructure.
- Robots needed to communicate across long distances in challenging terrain.

Solutions:

- Implemented a combination of autonomous drones and ground robots to create an adaptive, decentralized network.

3.6 Plan for how the mesh networking solution will be deployed for evaluation on hardware in WP5.

Despite these challenges, the solutions implemented in subterranean robotics often involve deploying communication infrastructure via robots. Since no pre-existing infrastructure is available, robots must carry, place, or relay communication nodes to create a functioning network. This approach ensures that data can be transmitted back to a central base or between robots, but it also adds complexity to mission planning and requires careful coordination to maintain connectivity. Thus, we choose an ad-hoc network, in which each robot can act as both a host and a client, dynamically forming a peer-to-peer communication mesh without relying on fixed infrastructure. This approach eliminates the need for deploying communication beacons via robots, as each unit inherently participates in data transmission and relaying. Ad-hoc networks offer flexibility, enabling robots to maintain connectivity even in dynamically changing environments where static relay nodes might become ineffective. Additionally, they enhance robustness by allowing multiple communication paths, reducing the risk of single points of failure. This self-organizing capability makes ad-hoc networks well-suited for abandoned mines.

To implement the ad-hoc network, we choose BATMAN (Better Approach To Mobile Ad-hoc Networking) as the routing protocol due to its decentralized and adaptive nature. BATMAN efficiently manages multi-hop communication by dynamically discovering and maintaining optimal routes between robots without requiring a central coordinator. This is particularly advantageous in subterranean environments, where network topology constantly changes due to robot movement and signal interference. Unlike traditional routing protocols, BATMAN distributes route knowledge across all nodes, ensuring that even if some robots lose direct connectivity, data can still be relayed through alternative paths. Additionally, BATMAN's lightweight overhead and self-healing capabilities enhance reliability, making it a suitable choice for maintaining continuous, robust communication in underground exploration missions.

Figure 25 : Communication network structure of a single machine.

Compared to other available ad-hoc networking protocols, BATMAN offers a more decentralized and resilient approach. Traditional protocols like OLSR (Optimized Link State Routing) require each node to maintain a complete map of the network, which can become inefficient in highly dynamic environments like subterranean exploration. In contrast, BATMAN distributes route discovery across multiple nodes, reducing overhead and making it more scalable for large, mobile robotic fleets. Another alternative, AODV (Ad-hoc On-Demand Distance Vector Routing), establishes routes only when needed, minimizing initial setup time but introducing latency during route discovery. BATMAN, on the other hand, continuously maintains best-effort routes, ensuring lower latency and faster recovery from link failures. These characteristics make BATMAN particularly well-suited for underground robotic missions, where connectivity can be intermittent, and rapid adaptation is essential.

3.6.1 Communication Protocols

In our system, we employ different communication protocols based on specific requirements. Given that we are using ROS 2, our choice of middleware and external communication mechanisms is tailored for efficient and reliable map data exchange.

3.6.2 Internal Communication: CycloneDDS

For internal communication within each robot, we utilize CycloneDDS as the ROS 2 middleware. CycloneDDS is an implementation of the Data Distribution Service (DDS) that ensures efficient and real-time communication between ROS 2 nodes.

While ROS 2 supports multiple DDS implementations (e.g., FastDDS, Connex DDS, OpenSplice DDS), we chose CycloneDDS because of:

- Lower latency and higher throughput: CycloneDDS has demonstrated superior real-time performance in ROS 2 benchmarks, making it well-suited for robotic applications.
- Automatic discovery efficiency: Compared to FastDDS and Connex DDS, CycloneDDS provides more reliable automatic discovery, reducing setup complexity.
- Lightweight and resource-efficient: It consumes fewer system resources than OpenSplice and Connex DDS, which is beneficial for embedded and low-power robotic platforms.
- Open-source and actively maintained: CycloneDDS is fully open-source, with strong community support and active development aligned with ROS 2 improvements.

CycloneDDS enables seamless communication between different ROS 2 components such as perception, planning, and control modules within each robot.

3.6.3 Robot-to-Robot Communication

For robot-to-robot communication and map sharing, we use communication-aware control to stream large data, as we need to enable collaborative autonomy and real-time map sharing in infrastructure-less underground environments. Unlike internal communication within a single robot, robot-to-robot communication must account for network variability, data volume, and mission-critical timing constraints. To address these challenges, our system integrates a communication-aware control framework inspired by recent advancements in 5G-enabled robotic coordination. This approach dynamically regulates the transmission of large map data, between robots, by adapting to the quality of the wireless link. Map instances are transmitted incrementally based on control signals derived from latency measurements (heartbeat messages), allowing robots to adjust transmission rates in real-time to avoid buffer overflows and network congestion. In scenarios where robots temporarily lose connectivity due to signal attenuation in complex underground structures, they continue to operate autonomously using locally stored maps, ensuring robustness against intermittent communication. Once connectivity is restored, buffered data are transmitted, and robots synchronize with updated transformations from the edge server or peer robots. This decentralized resilience, coupled with adaptive data flow control, ensures reliable multi-agent coordination without dependence on continuous infrastructure availability.

4 Partners Contributions

The UPAT team contributes by conducting an extensive survey and evaluation of state-of-the-art SLAM solutions suitable for deployment directly on-board robots in simulation. This evaluation enables a thorough comparison of mapping quality, localization accuracy, and error across different SLAM approaches. As part of this effort, DTU also generates point cloud (PCD) maps of various segments of the simulated mine, using different robots following partially overlapping trajectories to emulate realistic multi-agent exploration scenarios.

Building upon these outputs, LTU develops and applies a novel point cloud map merging algorithm specifically tailored for the needs of the PERSEPHONE project. This algorithm aligns and fuses the individually generated maps into a unified global representation, enhancing the spatial understanding of the environment.

Additionally, DTU contributes a survey on infrastructure-free mapping and machine-to-machine information sharing architectures, exploring how such systems can be developed using ROS 2-based communication frameworks. This supports the design of decentralized coordination strategies suited for constrained subterranean environments. Team EPIROC and MRP have joined the detailed discussion and brainstorming meetings related to task 4.4 to plan multi machine infrastructure free mapping and localization. Both teams have provided valuable insights into the problem, showcasing potential requirements from an end-user prospective.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable presented the work carried out under Task 4.4, focusing on real-time, infrastructure-free mapping and localization using multiple autonomous machines in underground mining environments. Building upon earlier efforts in navigation and terrain understanding, this report introduced a key advancement: the deployment and evaluation of SLAM algorithms specifically LIO-SAM and DLIO that operate solely using onboard LiDAR and IMU sensors, independent of any external infrastructure or ground truth positioning. Through simulation-based validation using ROS 2 and Gazebo, these SLAM methods were benchmarked in realistic mining scenarios. The experiments included single-robot evaluations as well as multi-robot trials where each Terrain Hopper robot generated local maps that were later merged using scan matching and descriptor-based techniques. This enabled the creation of a shared, collaboratively constructed map of the mine. In addition, the deliverable outlined a communication framework that enables coordination between explorer and deployer robots via infrastructure-free mesh networking. This architectural component fills a critical gap from previous tasks and supports seamless data sharing for SLAM, mapping, and task awareness. Together, these contributions demonstrate meaningful progress toward fully autonomous, collaborative exploration and mapping in GPS-denied, infrastructure-free environments. The results lay the groundwork for future real-world testing and hardware deployment in upcoming project phases.

6 Future Plans

Looking ahead, the work initiated in Task 4.4 will continue toward real-world deployment and experimental validation. A major milestone will be the field trial scheduled for September 2025 at the GM mine site in Athens, where we plan to collect extensive sensor data in a real subterranean environment. These experiments will serve as the basis for a thorough evaluation of the SLAM and communication systems developed so far and will be carried out as part of Work Package 5 (WP5), which focuses on integration and validation in operational settings. To improve system resilience and reliability under real-world conditions, we will extend the SLAM framework to include a fault-tolerant architecture that combines multiple odometry sources such as LiDAR-inertial, visual, and wheel-based odometry into a unified estimation pipeline. This multi-source approach is expected to enhance localization robustness in the presence of sensor degradation, dynamic lighting, or degraded LiDAR returns.

Additionally, the communication framework enabling collaborative autonomy will be further developed. We will implement more robust machine-to-machine coordination mechanisms to support efficient and reliable sharing of maps, local graphs, and exploration status among multiple agents. These enhancements will ensure consistent world understanding across robots and enable more advanced cooperative behaviors in complex and infrastructure-free environments. These future developments will play a critical role in transitioning the system from simulation to deployment and achieving the project's long-term objectives for autonomous, collaborative mining operations.

7 References

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